

Hierarchical planning for pharmaceutical preparedness in the event of disasters: A Delphi consensus study

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Received 5 February 2025 ♦ Accepted 9 March 2025 ♦ Published 4 April 2025

Citation: Ikaditya L, Zazuli Z, Hidayat YA, Adnyana IK (2025) Hierarchical planning for pharmaceutical preparedness in the event of disasters: A Delphi consensus study. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e148700>

Abstract

Cross-sector collaboration is a strategy employed in the realm of pharmaceutical disaster preparedness. The present study aims to integrate the roles of all stakeholders in the collaboration function through hierarchical planning. The Delphi method was employed as the primary research approach, specifically in the context of an expert consensus study. This method involved conducting a three-round Delphi survey, encompassing seven experts. The results of each round yielded an Interquartile Range (IQR) ≤ 20 , indicating a strong consensus among experts in assessing the parameters. Subsequently, these parameters were categorized based on hierarchical planning: strategic (8 parameters), tactical (9 parameters), and operational (13 parameters). The Delphi process was successful in achieving a consensus from diverse perspectives on collaborative efforts in pharmaceutical preparedness in the event of a disaster. These findings serve as a policy framework for defining stakeholder authority and responsibilities within the disaster mitigation cycle, particularly in the pharmaceutical sector.

Keywords

hierarchical planning, pharmaceuticals in disaster, Delphi technique, cross-sector collaboration

Introduction

Disasters have a profound impact on health, particularly that of the affected population. For this reason, the provision of health services is an integral component of humanitarian assistance in the aftermath of a disaster (Nazar and Nazar 2020). However, standard operations management is susceptible to failure during the event of disasters due to various challenges and pressures, which can adversely affect the health system. The nature of these events, which are often large and unpredictable, may necessitate unconventional responses and more complex response proce-

dures. The unpredictability of disasters further exacerbates the complexity of the emergency medical responses (Gulzari and Tarakci 2021), underscoring the necessity of comprehensive emergency preparedness plans prior to a major disaster (Chen and Wanbon 2023). Achieving disaster risk reduction necessitates a multifaceted approach that engages all stakeholders involved in disaster risk forecasting, prevention, management, and mitigation, along with the evaluation of consequences (Righi et al. 2021).

A critical component of disaster preparedness is stakeholder integration, underpinned by cross-sector collaboration (Lahiri et al. 2021). Within the health sector, the

involvement of pharmacists in disaster preparedness is a pivotal element (Watson et al. 2019). This contribution is of paramount importance, as disasters pose a significant threat to the management of pharmaceutical supply operations. Efficient management entails the intricate interplay of various interconnected components and the formulation of strategies to improve the resilience and responsiveness of pharmaceutical supply operations in diverse and evolving disaster scenarios (Ahmad Hamdi et al. 2024).

Barriers to cross-sector collaboration include ambiguity of team roles and overlapping work elements (Lahiri et al. 2021; Prasetyo et al. 2024). This can lead to misalignment in disaster problem-solving. Indeed, disaster risk reduction requires meticulous planning and the allocation of responsibilities among numerous stakeholders through networks to mitigate the severity and minimize the negative impacts of a disaster (Lahiri et al. 2021; Panneer et al. 2024). Consequently, novel and innovative approaches to disaster risk reduction that integrate knowledge and experience and facilitate dialogue among academics, practitioners, local government officials, and agencies to address common issues from different perspectives are imperative (Lahiri et al. 2021; Righi et al. 2021).

In consideration of the aforementioned points, the present study offers novel insights into the allocation of stakeholder responsibilities within the framework of hierarchical planning by incorporating diverse perspectives

to categorize strategic, tactical, and operational planning decisions. This study endeavors to propose solutions that address the collaborative efforts of interdependent sectors, such as government entities, professional organizations, educational institutions, pharmacists, and pharmaceutical logistics managers, to enhance disaster mitigation strategies. To this end, the study sought to address the following research questions: RQ1. What is the expert assessment of the established parameters related to pharmaceutical supply chain issues in disasters that form the basis for collaborative disaster management? RQ2. How can clustering these parameters to enhance the preparedness dimension of critical emergency management components be utilized?

Methods study design

The Delphi method has been utilized as a research approach in the context of expert consensus studies (Fig. 1), and it has been employed extensively in the domain of disaster research (Bisson et al. 2010; Rådestad et al. 2013; Zhong et al. 2015). Moreover, it is a common practice to employ the Delphi method to gather expert opinions for health policy development when the available evidence is limited (Meskell et al. 2014). Previous literature studies provided the foundation for this study’s questionnaire framework.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the study.

Research instruments

The research instruments were developed through a review of existing literature on the pharmaceutical supply chain in the context of natural and non-natural disasters (e.g., pandemic). The findings of the literature review were described in a research instrument in the form of close-ended and open-ended questions in a questionnaire. The research instrument consists of 4 parts, namely:

1. Informed consent in the form of willingness to participate voluntarily in research.
2. Identity of respondents
Input the respondent's identity in name, work experience, position, starting work, education, and field of expertise.
3. Close-ended questions
The close-ended questions in the instrument were designed with a 5-point Likert scale (Very Unimportant = 1; Not Important = 2; Neutral = 3; Important = 4; Very Important = 5). The number of closed questions consists of 23 questions divided into several aspects as follows:
 - a. Distribution = 6 question items
 - b. Prediction of Number and Type of Logistics = 5 question items
 - c. Logistics Inventory System = 5 question items
 - d. Supporting Resources = 7 question items
4. Open-ended questions
The open-ended question posed two distinct questions, namely, a list of critical infrastructure in the pharmaceutical logistics supply chain in a disaster and the necessity for additional parameters that had yet to be listed in the closed-ended question.

Selection of Delphi panel

The respondents of this study were selected based on their expertise in disaster-related fields, with a focus on regulators, practitioners, professional organizations, and academics (Lahiri et al. 2021; Righi et al. 2021). The selection criteria included individuals with a minimum of one year of experience and a comprehensive understanding of disasters. The study involved a total of seven experts, and the recommended number of panelists for the Delphi study is typically between six and twelve (Mary J. Tellefson et al. 2019). The list of experts involved in the present study can be found in Table 1.

Delphi rounds of the research

The data collection process spanned a period of two months, with deadlines established at two-week intervals. The study was conducted through online surveys using the Kuesio platform (<https://kuesio.id>), and the survey instrument link was disseminated via WhatsApp. A remind-

er or clarification was sent via WhatsApp one week later. The study was carried out in three rounds of research (Fig. 1). The reliability approach was generated by assessing the consensus reached in Rounds 1 and 2 and reporting their findings to the panel. The researcher's ability to effectively synthesize the panel's input from Round 1 can be gauged by the presence of consensus after Round 2 (Kanteler and Bakouros 2024). It is imperative to limit the number of surveys to 2–3 times to ensure optimal participation by experts and to maintain a substantial response rate (Manias-Muñoz et al. 2019; Melander et al. 2019). The implementation of the research is as follows:

1. Round 1: link submitted on 6 June 2023. The data obtained by data analysis show the question items have reached consensus by all experts.
2. Round 2: The link was sent on 8 July 2023. The data obtained from Round 2 is analyzed as in Round 1 to see the achievement of consensus.
3. Round 3: link submitted on 13 July 2023. The data obtained from Round 3 was analyzed as in the previous round to see the consensus reached, and it was the final Delphi survey.

Data analysis

The Delphi questionnaire is said to reach consensus if the standard deviation value is below 1.5 and the interquartile range (IQR) value is below 2.5 (Giannarou and Zervas 2014). The following IQR values are considered: An IQR of 0 indicates a very strong consensus, an IQR of $0 < IQR \leq 20$ indicates a strong consensus, an IQR of $20 < IQR \leq 25$ indicates a medium consensus, an IQR of $25 < IQR \leq 30$ indicates a moderate dissent, and an IQR of $IQR > 30$ indicates a strong disagreement. The following statistical tests were used: (1) Kendall's W, which was employed to ascertain the appropriateness of each expert's scores; and (2) the t-test, which was utilized to assess the consistency of expert answers in each round (Von Der Gracht 2012).

Ethical approval

The study was approved by the ethics committee of Universitas Padjadjaran Bandung. The research project number is 2303060418, with ethics study number 495/UN6. KEP/EC/2023, approved on 10 April 2023.

Results

The results of this study present answers to two research questions as presented in the previous section.

Parameter assessment consensus

The level of consensus reached at the conclusion of each round determines whether or not the research process requires additional rounds. The results from Round 1 (see

Table 1. The description of the panel expert.

No	Expert	Expertise	Experience in Disaster Management (Years)
1	Expert 1	Head of the Working Team for Management and Governance of Pharmaceutical Service Facilities at the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia	30
2	Expert 2	Head of the Preparedness Section in Tasikmalaya Regency	6
3	Expert 3	Chief Pharmacist for Disaster Response, Indonesian Pharmacist Association	10
4	Expert 4	Head of the Hajj and Disaster Team at the West Java Provincial Health Office	10
5	Expert 5	Disaster Volunteers	5
6	Expert 6	Disaster Health Management Researcher and Consultant at CHPM, Faculty of Medicine, Public Health and Nursing, Gadjah Mada University (UGM)	17
7	Expert 7	Head of the Health Logistics Work Team and BMN Crisis Center of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia	12

CHPM: Disaster division of the Center for Health Policy and Management.

Suppl. material 1) demonstrated that the IQR was less than or equal to 20, indicating a strong consensus among experts assessing the parameters in the questionnaire. The expert panel proposed additional parameters related to items not initially included in the Delphi survey questionnaire for open spaces. The results included seven additional parameters and one Round 1 result parameter with the smallest average value assessed by the expert panel. Consequently, a reassessment of these parameters was conducted in Round 2 (see Suppl. material 1).

In Round 3, measurement repetition was performed, combining the parameters from Rounds 1 and 2. A panel of experts reassessed 30 parameter items (see Suppl. material 1). Thus, in Round 3, the final parameters were obtained and studied based on their level of importance in affecting the pharmaceutical logistics supply chain in the event of disasters.

The consistency of the consensus formed was assessed through statistical analysis, employing Kendall's W test to assess the concordance of scores provided by each expert. Statistically, the significance of parameter assessment by each expert increased with each round iteration (p -value = 0.05). The resultant data exhibited a normal distribution, prompting further analysis with the t -test to evaluate the consistency of expert responses in each round. The statistical analysis revealed consistency in assessment across each round, with a p -value less than 0.05 ($p = 0.02$).

Parameter classification

The clustering technique, which allowed the extraction of in-depth results regarding the differences and similarities between the experts, was implemented (Kanteler and Bakouros 2024). Clustering is a technique used to observe the phenomenon of grouping data based on the similarity of each parameter. In this study, k -means clustering was utilized, employing the RapidMiner platform. To determine the optimal number of clusters in the dataset, the analysis used the elbow method. The results of the best clusters identified in this study are presented graphically in Fig. 2. As demonstrated in Fig. 2, the elbow point was located at axial point 2, and the number of clusters was 3.

Figure 2. Elbow method graph.

Consequently, the final results of the Delphi survey were made in 3 clusters.

In Round 3, hierarchical planning was grouped into strategic, tactical, and operational levels (Alvarez et al. 2020). The strategic level involves long-term plans (with a time horizon of more than five years) to achieve strategic objectives set by top management, such as the Ministry of Health. The tactical level aims to attain tactical goals, implementing specific parts of the strategic plan within a shorter period (with a time horizon of 1–5 years), focusing on strengthening preparations before a disaster occurs. The operational level, which is positioned below the tactical level, possesses a more limited scope, a more constrained timeframe (with a time horizon of less than one year), and entails lower-level management, specifically in the event of a disaster (Fig. 3).

Cluster 2 exhibited the highest number of parameters collected. The grouping results were achieved through matrix analysis (Fig. 4). The matrix demonstrates that the majority of parameter slices in cluster 2, between the tactical group and the question type group, predict the number of needs in the Delphi survey.

Figure 3. Grouping of the hierarchical planning.

Discussion

The study commenced with an assessment of the most critical parameters by the expert panel. The parameters formed in the research instrument reflect collaboration in disaster management, especially in pharmaceutical logistics management in the event of disasters. The strategic, tactical, and operational planning grouping approach was used as a collaboration function (Fig. 3). This division of planning levels is expected to expedite the resolution of disaster problems at the level of the subject implementing the parameters. The strategic-level settlement group comprises eight parameters, while the tactical level consists of nine parameters, and the operational level includes 13 parameters. This strategic function encompasses the role of government at the national level to ensure infrastructure reliability, disaster guidelines, funding, information technology, and command and control. This finding aligns with previous research, which demonstrated that the strategic-level collaboration framework in disaster preparedness involves the government's role in improving resource reliability, information technology security, command and control, and healthcare (Kanteler and Bakouros 2024).

At the tactical level, the role of regulators at the regional level and professional organizations is of partic-

ular importance, as are inventory reliability, planning, distribution, and human resources training. The operational level encompasses the majority of parameters, including implementation during a disaster. Therefore, strategies and tactics are crucial components at each stage, designed to minimize the impact of disasters on affected communities (BPBD 2010). During the mitigation stage, the emphasis on strategic and tactical priorities is crucial, as it involves preparation before a disaster occurs, aiming to reduce the number of victims and enhance readiness when facing disasters.

The planning level classification utilized a matrix framework to identify the correlation of parameters with the planning hierarchy (Fig. 4), with particular interest placed on the link between logistical needs and the tactical level. The parameters of the needs of vulnerable groups, the suitability of planning for potential disasters, the pharmaceutical industry's supply chain, and stock buffers based on disaster potential were the findings in this study. The four parameters were linked in one frame of pre-disaster logistics management. Concurrently, alternative frameworks yielded different frames among the matrix variables. This finding can serve as an essential tactical policy directive for disaster mitigation, as evidenced by the observation that pharmaceutical logistics

Figure 4. Parameter group linkage matrix analysis.

plans and emergency equipment should be prepared prior to a disaster (Blake et al. 2022; Hashimoto et al. 2023). A related study determined that medicines are regarded as strategic commodities in disaster contexts and must not have their supply chains disrupted, as this could precipitate a severe crisis (Goodarzian et al. 2020). This notion is further reinforced by the findings of previous studies, which underscore that the disruption of medicine availability, especially among vulnerable populations such as children and individuals afflicted with chronic diseases, is a primary concern in disaster contexts (Ochi et al. 2015).

The adequacy and type of logistics in response to a particular disaster are of equal significance, as evidenced by the findings of previous studies that erroneous projections of needs can lead to drug shortages or underutilization (Houston and Nickerson 2019; Alani et al. 2023). A further salient aspect within this frame pertains to the preparedness of the pharmaceutical industry in meeting its logistical obligations. This aspect underscores the pharmaceutical industry’s collaborative efforts to ensure the availability and accessibility of pharmaceutical products in disaster mitigation (Ashraf and Heavey 2023).

Strengths and limitations

As with other Delphi studies, the findings of the present study are contingent on the group of participants. Although efforts were made to ensure that the recruited experts had diverse backgrounds to avoid distorted results, it should be noted that consultations with different groups of participants may result in different estimates. Complete participation of participants is challenging in Delphi research, and the high retention rate of participants across all three rounds is a significant positive feature of this study. Another limitation of the present study is its relatively small sample size, which restricts the generalizability of its findings and the ability to draw definitive conclusions. However, this does not compromise the validity of the study's results, as the Delphi method places greater emphasis on the selection of expert participants than on statistical power (Okoli and Pawlowski 2004).

Conclusion

The Delphi consensus yielded parameters for disaster preparedness in the pharmaceutical sector, which are expected to be incorporated into the stakeholders' policy in the division of authority based on the planning hierarchy. An interesting finding emerged with respect to the logistics management of vulnerable groups in the event of disasters, preparedness planning for various disaster types, support for the pharmaceutical industry supply chain, and logistics stock buffers according to the nature of the disaster. These findings offer implications for future research, particularly in the area of enhancing pharmaceutical logistics management to improve disaster preparedness.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The Research Ethics Committee of Padjadjaran University Bandung provided ethical approval for this study (No. 495/UN6. KEP/EC/2023). Oral and written informed consent was obtained from all participants, with the understanding that all information was completely anonymous and would remain strictly confidential.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Funding

This work was supported by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No HK.01.07/F/1953/2022.

Author contributions

LI: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – original draft. ZZ: Methodology, Software, Validation, Supervision. Writing – review & editing. YAH: Conceptualization Visualization, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. IKA: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Validation.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Results of data analysis for each round

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Data type: pdf

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e148700.suppl1>